

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Disruptive innovations and marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of disruptive innovations on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The survey research design was adopted and a structured questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents. Three hundred and eighty four online marketers participated in the study. Personal data were analyzed using frequency count and simple percentages, while simple regression was used to test the hypotheses. The results showed that each disruptive innovation (social media, mobile payment technology, and mobile internet technology) had significant effect on marketing performance. Based on the findings, we concluded that adopting disruptive innovations for online marketing operations would enhance competitiveness and success of online marketing and business. It was therefore recommended that online marketers should henceforth understand and use the latest innovations to connect with their customers.

Keywords: Disruptive innovations; Marketing performance; Mobile internet technology; Mobile payment technology; social media

1. Introduction

Disruptive innovation (also called disruptive technology), is concerned with a new development that significantly alters the mode of operation of existing businesses (Corporate Finance Institute (CFI), 2022). It is used to describe how a new product or firm that started with simple applications or offerings, relentlessly moves up and replace established firms, alliances, or products. Disruptive innovation alters the way existing companies do business and negatively impacts the companies that fail to adapt. Because of such innovations, products that used to be available only to wealthy people, are now available to the wider consumer population. For instance, telephone, that was historically accessible only to the rich in Nigeria, is now available to everyone, courtesy of mobile telecommunication.

Thus, Twin (2022) defined disruptive innovation as that which transforms sophisticated or expensive products - previously accessible only to the creams of the society - to those that are more affordable and accessible to a boarder population. Twin further explained that such innovations and technologies can alter markets, by presenting affordable, simple, and accessible solutions.

From the foregoing, we can see that disruptive innovations, markets, and indeed marketing are strongly related. Marketing directs how markets work, and marketing success is affected by innovations. Afriyie, Du, & Musah (2019), found that innovation positively affects marketing performance. Thus, innovation is considered a critical factor in marketing.

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One innovation that has profoundly disrupted marketing practice, and has come to be a major determinant of marketing success is the internet. The internet has completely altered the way companies advertise and sell their products. Marketing on the internet delivers better results and revenues than marketing through the traditional channels, especially for small enterprises, with tight budgets. Sherman (2022), explained that it is not surprising that internet marketing fetches better revenues, because it is cheaper than traditional marketing. Thus, it is important for today's marketers to embrace the internet, to drive their marketing efforts. Internet (online) marketers should know how internet related innovations influence their success.

This study therefore aims at investigating the effect of internet-related disruptive innovations on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo.

Statement of Problem

Research has revealed that disruptive innovations could wipe out the equity of many established public companies (Thomas, 2021). Therefore, if long-established firms cannot withstand the impact of such innovations, then so it is with every company. Disruptive innovations can alter any industry and change the way companies sell their products (Rusine, 2022).

It is therefore pertinent for online marketers to understand the implications of these innovations to their core business. However, there is dearth of information on the subject in Nigeria. No study was found on disruptive innovations and marketing performance in Nigeria. This study therefore aims at contributing to filling the gap in literature by investigating the effect of internet-related disruptive innovations (such as social media, mobile payment and mobile internet) on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study was to investigate the effect of disruptive innovations on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

The specific objectives were to;

- Investigate the effect of social media on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.
- Determine the effect of mobile payment technology on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State
- Examine the effect of mobile internet technology on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated:

- Ho1: Social media has no significant effect on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State
- Ho2: Mobile technology has no significant effect on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State
- Ho3: Mobile internet technology has no significant effect on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

1.1. Research Model

Based on the hypotheses, the conceptual model below was constructed.

Figure 1 Research model of disruptive innovations and marketing performance Source: Researcher's construct, 2022

2. Literature Review

2.1. Understanding Disruptive Innovation

In 1997, Clayton Christensen, in his book “the innovator’s Dilemma: When New Technologies cause Great Firms to Fail” introduced the concept of disruptive innovation. It entails introducing new innovations, significantly different from existing ones, having the capacity to transform an industry completely (Rusine, 2022).

Different definitions of the term are found in literature. Harndman et al.(2013) defined disruptive innovations as innovations that are so different that their establishment in a market disrupts the pre-existing system. Accordingly, Daneels (2004), defined disruptive innovation as a specific kind of technological change which operates through a specific mechanism, having specific consequences. Windell(2007) noted that such innovations can alter the levels of competition among firms by changing performance level and business processes.

Disruptive innovation is also seen as the adoption of technologies that significantly transforms the way businesses are operated. This innovation can push companies to change the way they approach their business or risk losing market share and in some cases, becoming irrelevant (Singh & Hanafi, 2019).

2.2. Types of innovations that impact marketing

Rusine (2022) identified three types of innovations that impact marketing operation. The first type involves an innovation that makes something cheaper, faster or easier, eg. email. The second type involves improving something that already existed. For example, cloud computing, which involves improving computer storage to allow people to store data online, instead of having hard copies of everything. Another example is CRM software used in managing customer relationship, from anywhere at any time. The third type of innovation involves companies changing the way they run their operation. This could range from changing the way they sell products (like manufacturing company doing e-commerce) to using external organization to manage certain segments of their marketing process.

2.3. Current disruptions in the business world

Some innovations have disrupted the business world in recent years, impacting marketing, finances, banking, manufacturing and many other aspects of business. Rusine (2022) identified eight (8) types of such innovations. They include social media, cloud computing, big data, 3D printing, blockchain, mobile payments, machine learning tools, and robotics. Also, Bayo and Red-well (2020), quoting from the Mckinsey Global institute, Stated that there are twelve (12) forms of disruptive innovations which exhibit the greatest economic impact. They are: mobile internet, artificial intelligence,(A1), the internet of things, cloud technology, advanced robotics, autonomous and near autonomous vehicles, next generation genomics, energy storage, 3-D printing, advanced materials, advanced oil and gas explorations, and renewable energy. This study considered three of those identified innovations relevant to online marketing. They are social media, mobile payments, and mobile internet.

2.4. Social Media

Social media platforms such as Meta (formerly, Facebook), Twitter, Whatsapp, and linkedin are becoming increasingly popular destinations for consumers to learn about online companies and business. These platforms are used by companies to interact and build relationships with their target customers.

According to Revechat (2022), in order to maintain a competitive pace, businesses are bound to leverage popular media platforms. Social platforms help you connect with your customers, boost brand awareness, and increase your leads and sales. Social media helps companies a bigger audience. Social Media Examiner (2016) found that social media marketing efforts significantly increased exposure of companies to their target customers for business transaction.

2.5. Mobile Payment Technology

This technology has seriously disrupted how payments are made. Since many people now own mobile phones and carry their phones wherever they go, making payments on the go has become very important. The option of using mobile devices to make payments has made life simple. This idea is gaining popularity.

Adoption of mobile payment technologies is increasing all over the world because of the increase in the number of mobile consumers. This has a positive impact on global economy. Statista (2021) noted that rapidly increasing mobile consumer and P2P payments are fueling the global growth of mobile payment services.

This growing trend of mobile payments helps provide people with more flexibility, allowing customers to make payments without having to worry about having cash or credit/debit cards on hand (Forbes, 2018).

2.6. Mobile Internet Technology

Mobile internet subscribers in Nigeria grew from 40.63 million in 2018 to 72.57 million in 2021, and this number is likely to grow to 117.5 million in 2027 (Statista, 2022). Mobile internet technology consists of internet enabled devices like smartphones, tablets and many mobile devices. Today you do not necessarily need a computer to connect to the internet.

Connecting to the internet anytime and anywhere is now becoming a part of our lives. As long as one's phone is internet-enabled and one has data or Wi-Fi connection, one can easily access the internet from anywhere.

According to emarketer (2019), people now spend more of their time going online for a variety of purposes, and it is primarily the smartphone that is responsible for this online connectivity.

Since everyone is moving toward smartphone usage, the implication is that advertisers and marketers have to adjust their strategies accordingly to accommodate mobile. Presently, a company without a website that is mobile-friendly, risks losing valuable exposure on google web search queries. The reason being that in 2015, google changed its algorithm so that more mobile-friendly websites receive priority placement for search queries made on mobile device (investopedia, 2021).

2.7. Marketing Performance

Marketing performance helps marketers to determine how well their marketing activities are doing towards achieving the goals in their marketing plan. According to Wrike (2022), marketing performance involves aligning marketing team's goalsto actual results. It is measured using such indicators as revenues and sales, lead generation, customer retention, brand awareness and engagement. However, the indicator or metric used is dependent on a marketer's core objectives and plan. For example, a marketer may have the objective of increasing leads generation by 30% over the next year. In this case, performance should be measured based on the percentage of leads generated. In this study, we used sales and brand awareness to measure marketing performance.

2.8. Online Marketing

This is the practice of taking leverage of web-based platforms/channels to communicate a company's offering to the target market. Techopedia (2021) viewed online marketing as involving the promotion of goods and services on the internet using a set of tools as well as methodologies. Online marketing makes use of a wider array of marketing tools compared to the traditional marketing due to the availability of additional marketing mechanisms and channels on the internet. Online marketing helps companies to raise awareness of their brands by establishing their online presence across the internet.

Online marketing simply entails marketing online, as opposed to offline, traditional marketing. It includes marketing on social media sites and mobile apps. It can take place through computer, smartphones, digital devices, and other internet-enabled platforms (investopedia, 2022).

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1. Theory of Disruptive Innovation

The theory of disruptive innovation, also called Christensen's theory of disruptive technology, is a theory best used to discuss the impact of new and ground breaking innovations on a firm's existence. The theory was coined by Professor Christensen during his research on the disk-drive industry. It was later popularized using his book on innovator's dilemma in 1997.

The theory is used in explaining a situation in which an alters and transforms industry or market through the introduction of simple, convenience, accessible and affordable solutions (Christensen institute, 2022). Christensen explained that such innovations usually begin in a niche market that is not very attractive or considered inconsequential by incumbent firms in the industry, but eventually the new solution or product completely redefines the industry.

In his theory, Christensen made a distinction between sustainable innovations and disruptive innovations. He stated that sustainable innovations add value to existing and already established products whilst disruptive innovations disrupt or redefine performance level, and create a new marketplace (Anthony, 2004). The theory provides useful insight to business owners and managers on how such innovations can impact their operations and why many firms fail when confronted by those innovations.

According to Christensen, due to the fact that the nature of such innovations is unpredictable, successful and well managed firms can also be negatively affected. The theory also helps managers to determine when an idea or technology has become disruptive. It also provides guiding principles to new firms on how to commercialize such innovations (Chishakwe and Smith, 2012).

3.2. Review of empirical studies

Bissesar (2016) examined digital currency technology usage as a disruptive technology in the Caribbean with the objective to draw attention to the advantages and risks associated with the innovation. Three sources of data collection were used in the study. They were literature review, solicitation for experts' opinions, and a formal survey. The study revealed that the Caribbean could benefit from innovations in payment technology. It was also found that even though digital currency and mobile money technologies could contribute to the growth of the region, their development was however, retarded by the unwillingness of financial regulators to engage with them. The study failed to show the association between digital currency usage and the success of firms that embraced such payments.

Owuor (2018) studied disruptive technologies to see how they influence the performance of Kenyan insurance firms. The study was a review of literature that addressed technology and its relationship with insurance business performance. The result showed that many aspects of disruptive technology have a significant influence on the growth of insurance firms in Kenya. Furthermore, the study established the existence of a strong and positive connection between insurance strategies and business performance.

Singh & Hanafi (2019) examined disruptive technology and SMES performance in Malaysia. One hundred and fifty firms participated in the study. The results revealed a significant, positive relationship between disruptive technology and SMEs performance. The results also provided a great insight for various stakeholders to better understand the impact of disruptive technology.

Bayo & Red-well (2022) evaluated how disruptive technologies affect productivity of soft drinks manufacturing firms in south-south, Nigeria. Forty five senior managers in the soft drink manufacturing firms participated in the study. PPMC was used to analyze the data collected. Findings showed that all the disruptive technologies have a significant, positive relationship with productivity of the soft drink manufacturing companies. The researchers recommended that mobile internet technology and additive manufacturing should be embraced in the soft drink manufacturing industry to achieve enhanced productivity

Chishakwe & Smith (2012) examined disruptive technology and the success SMEs in a developing nation by studying King Williams Town in South Africa. A pretested questionnaire was administered to both owners and managers of SMES

in the area. The results revealed that disruptive technology alters how businesses operate. It was then concluded that disruptive technology affects the success of SMEs.

Afriyie, Du, & Musah (2019) studied how innovation affects marketing performance of SME in an emerging economy. Transformational leadership was used to moderate the effect. Data were collected from 437 SME service firms of a fast-growing service sector. Analysis was done using Partial least squares structural equation modeling, and the results revealed that innovation has a positive effect on marketing performance.

4. Methodology

4.1. Research Design

The survey research design was adopted for the study.

4.2. Population and Sample

The population comprised all online marketers - everyone who uses online channels to advertise and sell products or services in Uyo. A sample size of 384 online marketers that participated in the study was determined using the formula for infinite population by Walpole (1974) as follows:

$$n = \frac{Z_{\alpha/2}^2}{4e^2}$$

Where, n is the sample size, $Z_{\alpha/2}$ is the value obtained from the standard normal distribution at 5% level of significance.

$$Z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96, e = 0.05$$

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2}{4(0.0025)} = \frac{(1.96)^2}{0.01} = \frac{3.8416}{0.01} = 384$$

4.3. Sampling Technique

Convenience sampling technique was used. This technique allows a researcher to reach out to accessible respondents.

4.4. Research Instrument

A structured questionnaire was used in collecting data. The questionnaire comprised two sections: A and B. Section A contained the personal data of the respondents, while section B comprised five-points likert scale items for measuring the constructs.

4.5. Validity of the Instrument

To ensure the validity of the instrument, two copies of the instrument were given to two research experts within the university community, who made necessary corrections and inputs which were incorporated into the questionnaire before the final copy was produced and administered.

4.6. Reliability of the Instrument

Table 1 Reliability analysis of the instrument

Variables	No of items	Reliability coefficient
Social media	5	0.87
Mobile payment technology	5	0.78
Mobile internet technology	5	0.82
Marketing performance	4	0.80

The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha method. Twenty copies of the questionnaire were administered to 20 online marketers in Uyo, and the data obtained were used to computer reliability coefficient.

Table 1 contains the summary of the analysis

From above table, the reliability scores for all variables were above the 0.7 threshold of acceptable Cronbach Alpha value. Thus, the instrument was considered reliable.

4.7. Method of Data Analysis

Personal data of the respondents were analyzed using frequency count and simple percentages, while simple regression analysis was carried out on the hypotheses. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

5. Results

Table 2 Questionnaire distribution

Items	Number of copies of questionnaire	Percentage (%)
Returned and useable	371	96.61
Not returned and un-useable	13	3.39
Total	384	100

Table 2 indicates that out of 384 copies of questionnaire administered to the respondents, 371, representing 96.61% were returned in a useable form while the remaining 13 (3.39%) copies were either returned but not in useable form or not returned at all.

Table 3 Personal Data of Respondents

Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender		
MALE	179	48.2
FEMALE	192	51.8
Total	371	100.0
Age		
15-24	105	28.3
25-34	147	39.6
35-44	76	20.5
45 and Above	43	11.6
Total	371	100.0
Educational Qualification		
SSCE	85	22.9
ND/NCE	104	28.0
HND/BSc	112	30.2
Above BSc	70	18.9
Total	371	100.0

From table 3 above, it can be observed that 179 (48.2%) out of the 371 respondents were male while 192 (51.8%) of the respondents were female. The table also indicates that those between the ages bracket of 15-24 years were 105 (28.3%) of the respondents, 147 (39.6%) were those within the age bracket of 25-34 years, 76 (20.5%) were those within the age bracket of 35-44 years, while the respondents above the age of 45 years were 43 (11.6%).

Furthermore, the table indicates that those with first school leaving certificate made 22.9% (85) of the respondents, 104 (28.0%) of the respondents were those with ND/NCE, 112 (30.2%) of the respondents were HND/BSc holders and the remaining 18.9% (70) of the respondents were holders of educational certificates higher than BSc.

5.1. Test of Hypothesis One

5.1.1. H_{01} : Social media has no significant effect on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4 Model Summary for Hypothesis One

Model Summary				
#Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.881a	0.776	0.775	1.48172

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2806.592	1	2806.592	1278.335	0.000 ^b
	Residual	810.141	369	2.196		
	Total	3616.733	370			

a. Dependent Variable: Marketing Performance; b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	29.425	0.381		77.201	0.000
	Social Media	0.687	0.019	-0.881	-35.754	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Marketing Performance

The R value of 0.881 in the table indicates that there is a relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. The R-Square value of 0.776 implies that about 77.6% of the variation in marketing performance was explained by social media. The F-calculated value of 1278.335 implies that the model was adequate. The constant value of 29.425 indicates that keeping independent variable (social media) constant, marketing performance will remain at 29.425. The coefficient of social media was 0.687 which means that a unit change in social media will lead to 0.687 change in marketing performance. The P-value of 0.000 means that the effect of social media on marketing performance was statistically significant.

5.2. Test of Hypothesis Two

5.2.1. H_{02} : Mobile payment technology has no significant effect on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwalbom State.

Table 5 Model Summary for Hypothesis Two

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.876 ^a	0.767	0.766	1.51098

a. Predictors: (Constant), Mobile Payment Technology

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2774.286	1	2774.286	1215.164	.000 ^b
	Residual	842.447	369	2.283		
	Total	3616.733	370			

a. Dependent Variable: Marketing Performance; b. Predictors: (Constant), Mobile Payment Technology

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	29.408	0.390		75.336	0.000
	Mobile Payment Technology	0.694	0.020	-0.876	-34.859	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Marketing Performance

The table above with R value of 0.876 indicates that there is a significant relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. The R-Square value of 0.767 implies that about 76.7% of the variation in marketing performance was explained by Mobile payment technology. The F-calculated value of 1215.164 at 0.000 signifies that the model was adequate. The constant value of 29.408 indicates that keeping independent variable (Mobile payment technology) constant, marketing performance will remain at 29.408. The coefficient of Mobile payment technology was 0.694 which means that a unit change in Mobile payment technology will lead to 0.694 unit change in marketing performance. The P-value of 0.000 means that the effect of Mobile payment technology on marketing performance was statistically significant.

5.2.2. Test of Hypothesis Three

5.2.3. H_{03} : Mobile internet technology has no significant effect on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwalbom State.

Table 6 Model Summary for Hypothesis Three

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.864 ^a	0.747	0.747	1.57393

a. Predictors: (Constant), Mobile Internet Technology

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2702.623	1	2702.623	1090.972	0.000 ^b
	Residual	914.110	369	2.477		
	Total	3616.733	370			

a. Dependent Variable: Marketing Performance; b. Predictors: (Constant), Mobile Internet Technology

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	29.491	0.414		71.196	0.000
	Mobile Internet Technology	0.688	0.021	-0.864	-33.030	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Marketing Performance

The table above with R value of 0.864 indicates that there is a significant relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. The R-Square value of 0.747 implies that about 74.7% of the variation in marketing performance was explained by Mobile internet technology. The F-calculated value of 1090.972 at 0.000 implies that the model was adequate. The constant value of 29.491 indicates that keeping independent variable (Mobile internet technology) constant, marketing performance will remain at 29.491. The coefficient of Mobile internet technology was 0.688 which means that a unit change in Mobile internet technology will lead to 0.688 unit change in marketing performance. The P-value of 0.000 means that the effect of Mobile internet technology on marketing performance was statistically significant.

6. Discussion

The study revealed that disruptive innovations have a positive and significant effect on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The result of regression has shown that social media as disruptive innovation, when adopted by online marketer, can help bring about increased sales and brand awareness. Also, the result has shown that the use of mobile payment technology by online marketers can enhance their marketing success. Furthermore, the result has established that the use of mobile internet technology by online marketers will enhance their marketing success.

These findings agree with that of Chishakwe & Smith (2012) who found that disruptive innovations have a significant impact on the success of SMEs. The findings are also in support of Owuor (2018), which found that many aspects of disruptive technology have significant impact on organizational performance; particularly that mobile technology has a significant influence on the success of insurance firms in Kenya. Furthermore, the study confirms Bayo & Red-well (2020) who found mobile internet technology as significantly relating with the productivity of soft drink manufacturing firms.

Implications of the Study

This study has revealed that disruptive innovations have a significant effect on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. This implies that for online marketers to enjoy competitive advantage and continuous existence, they need to adapt disruptive innovations. Also, innovations such as social media, mobile payment technology and mobile internet technology are critical for the success of online marketing and business in Nigeria.

Summary

This study aimed at investigating the effect of disruptive innovations on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Questionnaire was used in collecting data and simple regression was used in testing the hypotheses.

The result of the first hypothesis showed that social media has a significant effect on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

The second hypothesis revealed that mobile payment technology has a significant effect on marketing performance of online marketers.

The third hypothesis stated that mobile internet technology does not significantly affect marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The results showed that mobile internet technology significantly affects marketing performance of online marketers.

7. Conclusion

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of disruptive innovations on marketing performance of online marketers in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. The study showed that innovations such as social media, mobile payment technology, and mobile internet technology have significant effects on marketing performance. Thus it is concluded that adapting disruptive innovations for online marketing operations can enhance competitiveness and success of online marketing and business

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings, the following recommendations were made:

- Online marketers should understand and learn to use the latest disruptive technologies to connect with their customers
- Social media, mobile payment technology, and mobile internet technology should be used by online marketers to enhance their marketing success.

Suggestion for Future Research

Future studies should be conducted to show the effects of other disruptive innovations such as cloud computing, big data, blockchain, robotics etc on marketing performance. Also, further studies should be conducted to determine which of the social media handles is most significant in enhancing online marketing success.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest among the three authors.

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